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AN EVALUATION OF THE IMPACT OF THE THEME- BASED APPROACH ON YOUNG LEARNERS' SPEAKING DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article explores the impact of using a theme-based approach on improving young learners' speaking abilities. It highlights a meaningful and engaging approach to language practice, and demonstrates how integrating language learning with meaningful content can create memorable and engaging experiences.

Key words: primary education, young learners, theme-based approach, speaking skills, content-based instruction (CBI), communicative approach, integrative approach, learner-centered approach, activities.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilarning gapirish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda mavzuga asoslangan yondashuvdan foydalanishning ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Unda til amaliyotiga mazmunli va jozibador yondashuv taqdim etiladi, shuningdek, til o'rganishni mazmunli kontent bilan integratsiyalash orqali esda qolarli va qiziqarli tajribalar yaratish yo'llari ko'rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: boshlang'ich ta'lim, kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalar, mavzuga asoslangan yondashuv (theme-based approach), gapirish ko'nikmalari, kontentga asoslangan ko'rsatma (CBI – content-based instruction), kommunikativ yondashuv, integrativ yondashuv, o'quvchi shaxsiga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv, mashqlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается влияние использования тематического подхода на улучшение разговорных навыков младших школьников. Представлен содержательный и увлекательный подход к языковой практике, а также показано, как интеграция изучения языка с содержательным контентом может создавать запоминающиеся и увлекательные впечатления.

Ключевые слова: начальное образование, младшие школьники, тематический подход (theme-based approach), навыки говорения, обучение на основе содержания (CBI – content-based instruction), коммуникативный подход, интегративный подход, личностно-ориентированный подход, упражнения.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching English speaking skills to young learners is both demanding and highly rewarding, presenting unique challenges for educators. These learners are naturally sociable, energetic, playful, and curious. As they are still in the process of cognitive and linguistic development, they can internalize language rules through exposure to comprehensible input and are receptive to the classroom environment. Language acquisition for young learners often occurs through play, which supports not only communication but also broader social development. Engaging with language in playful contexts is an instinctive and effective method for developing speaking abilities in a foreign language. As young learners typically have short attention spans—particularly at the initial stages of learning—it is essential to incorporate a diverse range of activities, classroom arrangements, and learner-centered strategies. Employing innovative, child-focused methodologies in the primary English classroom provides meaningful and memorable language practice.

Twenty-first-century education demands that teachers focus their instruction on developing so-called 21st-century skills, such as critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication, and different fields of literacy. Furthermore, in the modern approach, the target language is used both for communication and through its meaningful use ^[7].

Among these new approaches, the theme-based model of content-based instruction stands out as an effective and creative method, significantly contributing to both language acquisition and the development of speaking skills. The theme-based approach integrates language learning with meaningful content, providing young learners with engaging contexts to develop speaking skills. This approach aligns with the idea that chil-

children learn languages more effectively when they can relate new information to their existing knowledge and experiences. By organizing instruction around themes, teachers can create cohesive and immersive learning environments that promote oral communication ^[5].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theme-based approach, also known as thematic learning or instruction, involves selecting and highlighting a theme across instructional units, promoting interdisciplinary connections. This method is particularly effective in language teaching, where themes provide a cohesive structure for vocabulary and grammar instruction, facilitating improved speaking skills among young learners ^[9].

Studies have shown that the theme-based approach, as one of the modern approaches to teaching, can significantly improve primary school learners' speaking performance, including vocabulary usage, intonation, and fluency. By engaging with content that is organized around themes, learners are more likely to participate actively in speaking activities, leading to enhanced oral proficiency ^[8].

Cameron emphasizes the importance of contextualised language learning for young learners. She advocates for meaningful, topic-based communication activities in the classroom. Her work stresses that thematic units provide authentic situations where learners can practise oral skills naturally. Cameron also highlights the role of interaction and child-centred approaches, aligning closely with theme-based learning as it motivates learners by relating language to their interests and experiences ^[1].

Krashen's Input Hypothesis argues that learners acquire language best when exposed to comprehensible input slightly above their current proficiency ($i+1$) ^[3]. Theme-based instruction provides a rich, contextualised input that makes new language easier to understand and learn. His emphasis on natural communication supports thematic learning, since themes create meaningful contexts for language use, which encourages spontaneous speaking and reduces affective filters (anxiety, lack of motivation) ^[3].

James Cummins states the importance of cognitive academic language proficiency and supports thematic approaches that integrate language with content knowledge, supporting deeper understanding and language use ^[6]. Rod Ellis highlights the role of meaning-focused input and output in language acquisition. His work on task-based language teaching (TBLT) shows that meaningful tasks based on real-world themes promote speaking skills development. Ellis argues that thematic tasks allow learners to negotiate meaning, practise fluency, and receive feedback in communicative contexts.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Theme-based approaches can be considered a form of integrated task-based learning, where language is embedded in relevant topics ^[2]. Thus, theme-based learning in primary education provides engaging, meaningful, and interactive contexts that support young learners' speaking development by offering comprehensible and relevant input ^[3], encouraging authentic communication in a supportive environment ^[1], facilitating task-based, meaningful speaking practice ^[2], and promoting interaction and cognitive engagement ^[6]. Moreover, this approach offers an exciting and engaging way to develop young learners' speaking skills by integrating various interactive and dynamic activities, such as role plays, storytelling, discussions, and games. Thus, teachers can foster confidence, fluency, and creativity in young learners.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Implementing theme-based learning in primary classrooms helps maintain learners' motivation and reflects the way children naturally learn. This approach supports the development of thinking skills and encourages learners to make connections between different subject areas, enhancing their speaking abilities through integrated learning experiences. The following theme-based activities are used in primary education in order to improve young learners' speaking skills:

Information Gap Tasks. In this activity, young learners are supposed to work in pairs. One student has the information that the other partner does not have, and the partners share their information. Information gap activities serve many purposes, such as solving a problem or collecting information. Each partner plays an important role, because the task cannot be completed unless both partners provide the information each other needs.

For example: Young learners are asked to find information about three children – Mel, Kim, and Alex's talents.

- Pupil 1: Mel is good at sports. What about Kim? Kim is...
- Pupil 2: Kim is fond of singing songs. Does Alex like playing the guitar?
- Pupil 1: No, she likes taking photos. When does the School Talent Show begin? ...

While doing this activity, we can see the integration of English with Math (asking about time), Music (speaking about musical instruments), and Nature (describing the environment).

Picture-Based Discussions. Using visuals related to a theme such as “Weather” or “School”, pupils describe what they see, compare images, or create short stories. This supports vocabulary building, descriptive language, and structured speech. For example, describing different parts of a daily routine (Theme: Daily Life) helps learners practise time expressions and sequencing vocabulary. This activity also demonstrates the integration of English with other subjects such as Mathematics (through questions about time), Science, or Nature (by describing natural elements). Role-Play Activities give learners the opportunity to practise language in meaningful social contexts. This type of activity promotes fluency and social interaction.

For example, in a “Doctor–Patient” scenario under the theme of “Health”, pupils use functional language to describe symptoms and give advice. So, theme-based speaking activities are essential tools in the primary English classroom. They offer meaningful contexts, support language learning through interaction, and foster motivation and confidence.

In order to investigate the effectiveness of implementing the theme-based approach to teaching speaking in primary education, we prepared a questionnaire consisting of six questions and conducted a survey among 38 English language teachers who teach English in primary classes. Questionnaire on developing young learners’ speaking skills through a theme-based approach in primary education.

1. What is your teaching experience?

2-3 years - more than 5 years - more than 10 years -

2. Have you ever used “Theme/Content-based approach” in teaching English in primary education?

Yes - No -

3. How often do you integrate different subjects, such as Math, Science, Technology, PE, Art into your EFL lessons?

Always - Sometimes - Never - Rarely -

4. Which of the following activities do you use to develop speaking skills through a theme-based approach? (You can select more than one)

Role plays- Picture description-

Show and tell - Games -

Guessing games - Question-and-answer sessions-

“Find someone who” - Find the difference” -

Storytelling/ Story completion -..... Chain/Picture story-

5. Do you believe that activities based on theme-based approach to teaching English is useful in improving young learners’ speaking skills?

Yes, significantly - Why?

No, not much - Why not?

6. What challenges have you faced in using a theme-based approach for developing speaking skills, as well as integrating different subjects, such as Math, Science, Technology, PE, Art into your lessons? (Select all that apply)

Limited time for speaking activities-

Students’ lack of motivation or interest-

Difficulty in managing classroom behavior during activities-

Lack of resources or materials-

Difficulty in adapting activities for different levels-

Results of the Questionnaire. According to the 1st question, we identified that among 38 respondents, 12 have more than 10 years of teaching experience, 17 have been teaching English for more than 5 years, and 9 respondents have been working as English teachers for 2–3 years. This shows that most teachers have been teaching English for more than 3 years and are aware of how to organize various speaking activities and how to develop learners’ communication skills in primary education.

Based on the findings of the 2nd question, we discovered that not all the teachers/respondents are aware of the theme-based approach. Only 72% of them try to implement this approach in teaching speaking to young learners, while the remaining teachers mostly use traditional methods. From the respondents' answers to the 3rd question, we explored the following: most teachers consistently integrate Math, Art, and Nature into their EFL lessons to develop their younger learners' speaking skills.

Figure 1: Comparison of cross-curricular integration

The outcome of question 4 reveals that 100% (all 38 teachers) of respondents use communicative games, 97% (34 teachers) implement picture description and "Show and Tell" activities, and 91% (32 respondents) organize "Find Someone Who" activities and question-and-answer sessions to develop young learners' speaking skills.

Figure 2: Implementation of theme-based activities in teaching speaking

Considering the participants' responses to the 5th question, we determined their opinions about the importance of using a theme-based approach to improve young learners' speaking skills. From the responses, we understood that they prefer learner-centered classes over traditional ones, as centering instruction around themes allows for deeper engagement and enhanced oral communication abilities.

Before analyzing the answers to the 6th question, we divided respondents into two groups—young and experienced teachers—based on their teaching experience. According to their responses, both groups reported various challenges when integrating a theme-based approach to develop speaking skills across subjects such as Mathematics, Science, Technology, Primary IT, and Art. One of the most significant difficulties noted by experienced teachers (84%) and young teachers (58%) was the limited time available for speaking activities. A majority of young teachers (82%) also reported issues with managing classroom behavior during such activities, compared to only 24% of experienced teachers, suggesting that classroom management is a greater concern for less experienced educators. Lack of resources and materials emerged as a common obstacle across both groups, with 88% of experienced teachers and 70% of young teachers indicating this as a challenge. Furthermore, adapting activities for different proficiency levels was particularly problematic for young teachers (88%) compared to 48% of experienced ones. Student motivation and interest was a moderate chal-

lenge, cited by 47% of young teachers and 34% of experienced ones, pointing to a need for more engaging and relevant thematic content.

Figure 3: Challenges in implementing theme-based speaking activities

Having analyzed the questionnaire results, we understood that the theme-based approach serves as an effective method for developing young learners' speaking skills in primary education. By embedding speaking tasks within cross-curricular thematic units, this approach provides meaningful, engaging, and contextually rich opportunities for learners to use English communicatively. It not only enhances oral fluency and vocabulary acquisition but also fosters learner motivation and participation by connecting language learning to real-world themes.

Despite some challenges—such as limited instructional time, classroom management issues, and the need to adapt activities to varying proficiency levels—teachers acknowledged the pedagogical value of this approach. Overall, the theme-based model supports a learner-centered, integrated form of instruction that contributes significantly to the development of young learners' speaking competence.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can state that the theme-based approach plays a significant role in enhancing young learners' speaking abilities. Teachers reported that integrating speaking tasks into cross-curricular thematic units—such as Science, Mathematics, Technology, and Art—provides a meaningful and context-rich environment for language use. This method encourages learners to engage in natural communication while developing both subject knowledge and language competence. Participants noted that thematic lessons foster greater motivation and participation among learners, particularly when topics are relevant to their interests. The approach also supports vocabulary development and improves fluency by embedding speaking activities within familiar, real-world contexts.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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